

DECODING THE THEORETICAL UNDERPINNINGS AND NOMOLOGICAL NETWORK OF GREEN HRM AND EMPLOYEE GREEN BEHAVIOUR: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF LITERATURE

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Abstract

Purpose: The increasing global focus on environmental challenges has prompted organizations to integrate sustainable practices, driven by both regulatory compliance and the pursuit of competitive advantage. In response, Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM) has emerged as a pivotal approach to align HR functions with sustainability objectives and to promote environmentally responsible behavior among employees. This paper aims to systematically review the existing literature on the relationship between Green HRM and Employee Green Behaviour.

Design/methodology/approach: This study undertakes a comprehensive review of 55 empirical quantitative studies published between 2011 and 2024, focusing on the nexus between Green HRM practices and green employee behavior. The analysis identifies key theoretical frameworks and mediator-moderator models that explain this relationship. **Findings:** The review uncovers various theoretical perspectives that have been employed to examine Green HRM's influence on employee behavior. Additionally, the study highlights the diverse mediators and moderators that have been explored within this body of literature. **Originality/value:** This paper represents the first comprehensive review of the connection between Green HRM and Employee Green Behavior. By synthesizing empirical evidence, it outlines significant implications for both researchers and practitioners and proposes a comprehensive agenda for future research in this evolving field.

Keywords: *Green HRM, Employee Behavior, Sustainability, Comprehensive Review, Mediator-Moderator Frameworks, Theoretical Lens.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The degradation of the environment is perhaps the most catastrophic activity that the world is facing today (Hooi et al. 2022). The enormous deforestation, fossil fuel burning and decarbonization is manifesting a big question on environmental sustainability (Fawehinmi et al. 2020). As the society has increased its awareness towards the anthropogenic effects of the environment, there has been an increased pressure on the organizations for environmental protection (Ye et al. 2022). Therefore, protection of the environment is not just considered a social responsibility, which organizations should practice, but also a prominent source of their competitiveness (Porter and Kramer 2011). In order to protect the environment and build a competitive edge, organizations have set up certain rules and regulations, which are formulated to preserve the environment and create awareness among organizations to adapt green practices. But it has been found that the operationalization of

these ecological strategies still remains at a nascent stage (Hooi et al. 2022). Therefore, stakeholders of different organizations across the globe have been seeking for a greater accountability of environment friendly practices (Paillé et al. 2013), which led the corporate houses towards the transformation of their business models from traditional to green (Schaltegger and Wagner 2011). Literature has noted the role of such green models on the organization's competitive advantage (Jackson and Seo 2010). The organizations which are paying more attention to adopting green models achieve efficiency and effectiveness within their internal system and therefore diminish environmental wastage (Masri and Jaaron 2017) and obtain long-term viability (Paillé et al. 2014). Sustainability at the workplace begins with individual action and this demarcates that employees play a very prominent role in the successful execution of organizational green practices (Ciocirlan 2017); hence, their green behaviours play a crucial role in implementation company's green strategy (Pham and Paillé 2020 ; Jackson 2012). The past researches have shown that organizations which focus on deploying green employee practices will also enhance their sustainable business performance (Zhao and Huang, 2022).

This can be done by managing the pro-environmental aspects in the routine human resource management (HRM) practices (Hooi et al. 2022). Many businesses strive to create and implement a formal Environmental Management System (EMS) to derive the benefits of green practices (Masri and Jaaron 2017). Organizations need to transition towards green-oriented strategies (Aboramadan and Karatepe 2021) through utilizing HRM as a function in order to render environment-friendly HRM practices (Schaltegger et al. 2013). Therefore, the evolving concept of green HRM has been used to address the growing apprehensions regarding the environment related concerns of the organizations (Shah and Soomro 2023; Yusoff et al. 2020). Green HRM has fetched huge attention from many scholars recently (Nejati et al. 2017; Ren et al. 2018; Tang et al. 2018; Pham and Paillé 2020). It entails HRM practices that trigger positive environmental outcomes (Kramar 2014) through cultivating green orientation in traditional HR processes like recruitment & selection, training & development, evaluating and rewarding green performance, and maintaining an eco-friendly organizational culture (Renwick et al. 2013). Green HRM results in the reduction of environmental waste through systematically aligning its practices to promote pro-environmental employee behaviour (Rayner and Morgan 2018). In the last decade, green HRM has been practiced focusing on the alignment of eco-friendly practices (Arulrajah et al. 2015), to enhance optimum utilization of resources (Zibarras and Coan 2015). It enables the transition from outdated, traditional competencies to more green oriented competencies (Singh et al. 2020). Green HRM helps in streamlining the employee green behavioural and attitudinal changes and thus enhances the organizational environmental performance (Taylor et al. 2012). Therefore, it becomes extremely necessary for the organizations to stimulate their employee's green behaviours and attitudes aligned with their green goals (Nisar et al. 2021).

Ciocirlan (2017) stated that individual action is the starting point for workplace sustainability at the macro level. Employees are crucial in implementing the organization's green policy and hence their environmentally friendly actions are significant. Hence, it is imperative for organizations to adopt green HRM practices to encourage and motivate employees to engage in both in-role and extra-role environmentally friendly behaviours. This will aid organizations in attaining high-quality growth, preserving ecological equilibrium, and fostering inclusive well-being for individuals (Paillé et al. 2020; Norton et al. 2014). Nevertheless, the extent to which employees engage in

environmental conservation initiatives is contingent upon the organization's green HRM strategies (Pham and Paillé 2020). Hence, it is imperative for organizations to adopt green HRM practices to encourage and motivate employees to engage in both in-role and extra-role environmentally friendly behaviours. Employee's involvement in the green activities is shaped by green HRM practices that in turn helps to promote employees in-role and extra-role green behaviours (Norton et al. 2014; Paillé et al. 2020). In-role green behaviours represent daily task related green behaviours required to improvise the environmental performance of the organization by introducing green jobs and duties of the employees (Ones and Dilchert 2012). Thus, in-role green behaviours are linked with job descriptions of the employees where certain green tasks needs to be performed and extra-role green behaviours represent voluntary green behaviours which are neither required nor awarded but still employees perform them (Dyne et al. 1994; Zhang et al. 2019).

Realizing the seminal role of green HRM and employee green behaviours, extensive research attention has been given to map the antecedents and outcomes of both variables. There has been ample literature available on nomological network of green HRM (Paulet et al. 2021; Ren et al. 2018; Renwick et al. 2013; Amrutha and Geetha 2020; Yong et al. 2020) and employee green behaviour (Norton et al. 2015 ;Tang et al. 2023; Katz et al. 2022; Unsworth et al. 2021). Additionally, empirical research has highlighted the positive relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour (Chaudhary 2020). Nevertheless, less consideration has been given to delineate the intervening process (mediators) and boundary conditions (moderators) under which green HRM impacts employee green behaviour (Hooi et al. 2022). Mapping the mediators and moderators would help understand how and when green HRM influences employee green behaviour. Hence, a comprehensive literature review is required to bridge the gaps of previous literature by extending the understanding of green HRM practices with employee green behaviour. A systematic literature review has been used to fill this gap by examining the literature corpus of green HRM and employee green behaviour. The purpose of this review is to schematize and identify the possible mediators and moderators along with highlighting the possible theoretical lenses used in linking green HRM and employee green behaviour. In line with the literature and based on the present reviews of green HRM and employee green behaviour separately, that have been examined, the focus will be on identification of certain knowledge gaps with possible prominent issues to reflect in the future studies.

The important research questions (RQ's) that are developed in the form of below mentioned RQs:

RQ1: Which are the variables used as mediators between green HRM and employee green behaviour at the individual, team and organizational level?

RQ2: Which are the variables used as moderators between green HRM and employee green behaviour at the individual, team and organizational level?

RQ3: Which are the most used theories referred in researches studying the relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour?

This review adds to the existing literature in many ways. Firstly, this comprehensive review examines the relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour and provides a cogent understanding of intervening process and boundary conditions between the two variables. Secondly, it contributes to the literature by critically analysing the nomological network at the

individual, team and organizational level of the mediators and moderators. Thirdly, this review analyses the literature by analysing various theoretical frameworks used in green HRM and employee green behaviour researches by different disciplines. The findings of this review shall help the researchers in providing directions for future research.

The following is the breakdown of the review's structure. The next section represents methodology section of the study. Findings and discussions are highlighted in the further sections followed by theoretical and practical implications. The subsequent section focuses on the future research directions, policy recommendations and limitations. The study ends with conclusion section.

2. METHODOLOGY

A systematic literature review (SLR) approach has been followed to investigate the above mentioned RQ's. The purpose of opting for SLR are manifold A) it is considered scientific (Tranfield et al. 2003); B) it provides higher quality processes and outcomes (Leonidou et al. 2017); C) it reduces biasedness to a great extent (Dada 2018); D) it provides greater validity (Wang and Chugh 2014) and E) it provides a clear map of investigated research areas (Kauppi et al. 2018). As per our knowledge, it is the first literature review conducted to explain the relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour.

• Inclusion criteria

PEO model ('People, Exposure, Outcome') is adopted as a guiding mechanism in developing the inclusion criteria for the review (Moola et al. 2015). The PEO model used in this research is based on (P) green HRM and employee green behaviour contexts, (E) examine green HRM in terms of synonyms, conventions, and concepts in relation to, (O) employee green behaviour. The inclusion criteria used are as follows: All studies included should 1) be peer-reviewed research papers in academic journals, 2) include articles written in English language, 3) comprise of only empirical quantitative research papers in the organizational context, 4) be statistically proven between green HRM and employee green behaviour. This review has not taken into consideration any proceedings paper, retracted publications, books, book chapters, conference paper, meeting abstracts and review articles. Sustainable HRM is not included in the search strings because the term 'Sustainable HRM' and 'Green HRM' are conceptually different where green HRM is a subset in the field of sustainable HRM. As defined by Kramar (2014), sustainable HRM being an umbrella concept involves the social, financial and ecological aspects of HRM whereas green HRM as a concept focuses on that part of HR management dealing with the environmental goals (Wagner 2013).

This SLR has included 55 full text empirical quantitative research papers published between 2011 and 2024 from the leading databases like SCOPUS, Web of Science, Science Direct, EBSCO, and Google Scholar. The databases like Scopus and Web of Science have been considered as the most extensive and insightful databases among academicians, governments, and business houses (Kamboj and Rahman 2015). The time period between 2011 and 2023 has been selected because after 2010, UN Global Compact released various Principles for Responsible Management Education (PRIME) that uplifted the morale of managers and scholars in advancing the knowledge regarding environmental awareness in organizational realm (Tanova and Bayighomog 2022). Another rationale for choosing the time period from 2011 to 2023 is that the application of green HRM was introduced 2011 onwards and green behaviour got highlighted in 2013 onwards, therefore

researchers found relevant literature linking green HRM and employee green behaviour after 2011.

- **Search strings used**

The following twelve search strings have been used in databases like Scopus, Web of Science, Science Direct, EBSCO ProQuest and Google scholar to obtain the relevant research papers:

Group 1 – green HRM OR green behaviour of employees OR organizational sustainability

Group 2 – green HRM OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 3 – green human resources management OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 4 – green human resources management OR green behaviour of employees OR organizational sustainability

Group 5 – green human resources management OR green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 6 – green HRM OR green behaviour OR organizational AND sustainability

Group 7- green human resource management OR green HRM AND green behaviour OR employee green behaviour OR pro-environmental behaviour OR OCBE

Group 8 – green recruitment OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 9 – green selection OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 10 – green training & development OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 11 - green performance & appraisal OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

Group 12 – green compensation & rewards OR employee green behaviour OR organizational sustainability

These twelve search strings are intended to include research papers on green HRM, green behaviour and their allied terms. Presuming that these databases might not pick up every prominent paper in this domain, search has also been conducted on reputed journals such as the International Journal of Manpower, Journal of Cleaner Production, Asia Pacific Journal of Management, Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management and Journal of Environmental Planning and Management which often publish papers on these relevant issues. PRISMA Framework 2022 (Vaio et al. 2022) has been used to extract the research papers from leading databases like Web of Science, Scopus, Science Direct, EBSCO ProQuest and Google Scholar. An initial search led to identification of 1745 research papers. Following this, an attempt was made in eliminating the duplicates which are directly or indirectly not related with green HRM and employee green behaviour, resulting in the removal of 410 duplicates papers. The 1335 research papers are further screened for eliminating proceedings paper, retracted publication, book chapters, conference papers, meeting abstracts and reviews resulting in 958 research papers. After going through the abstracts of these 958 research papers, 90 full text research papers are found which included green HRM and employee green behaviour. As the SLR focuses on empirical quantitative research papers, a total of 55 research

papers are finally considered. Lastly, MS Excel and Vos viewer are used to analyse these 55 research papers based on the key research questions.

The research design of the SLR has been structured in four main steps as represented in Figure-1.

Figure-1

Source: Adapted from Vaio et al., 2022

3. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Mediating Variables used between green HRM and Employee green behaviour

Mediating variables help in understanding the mechanism underlying the relationship between independent and dependent variables. These variables help in identifying and testing correlation between two variables by gaining a deeper insight. Sometimes, the independent variable may not directly affect the dependent variable and that's when, mediating variables helps in establishing a relation between the antecedent and the outcome (MacKinnon et al. 2012). As shown in Table-1, the mediating variables used between 'green HRM and employee green behaviour' are largely at the individual level (72.13%) such as psychological green climate, green commitment, green work engagement, green perceived organizational support, green work climate perception, employee green attitude etc and (21.31%) of the studies have used organizational level variables like perceived external prestige, green organizational identity, corporate social responsibility etc. to understand the organizational perspective on green HRM to green policy formulation and its implementation at the organisational level as a whole. Very limited number of studies (6.56%) have used team level mediating variables like collective green crafting, green knowledge sharing. These

two have been used to share and inspire the environment friendly policies across the team to achieve group goals. The explanation for using majorly individual level and organizational level mediating variables could be the convenience of researchers in collecting the data from the employees or from the organizations and as data collection at team level is usually complex (Foster, 2014) hence, very low number of researches have been conducted at the team level.

Table 1: Mediating variables used at the Individual, Team and Organizational level

Serial Number	Variables	Individual/ Team/ Organizational Level	No. of Studies
1	Green Culture	Organizational	2
2	Corporate Social Responsibility	Organizational	3
3	Green Organizational Identity	Organizational	1
4	Enablers of Green Culture: Leadership Emphasis; Message Credibility; Peer Involvement; Employee Empowerment	Organizational	1
5	Green HRM	Organizational	4
6	Responsible Leadership	Organizational	1
7	Green Intellectual Capital	Organizational	1
8	Collective Green Crafting	Team	1
9	Green Knowledge Sharing	Team	1
10	In-role team green behaviour	Team	1
11	Extra-role team green behaviour	Team	1
12	OCBE	Individual	2
13	Perceived External Prestige	Individual	1
14	Psychological Green Climate	Individual	3
15	Anticipated Environmental Emotions (Pride and Guilt)	Individual	1
16	Green Commitment	Individual	4
17	Green Work Engagement	Individual	1
18	Perceived Insider Status	Individual	1
19	Environmental Awareness	Individual	1
20	Green Supporting Climate	Individual	1
21	Green Satisfaction	Individual	1
22	Environmental Knowledge	Individual	1
23	Organizational Identification	Individual	2
24	Green Employee Empowerment	Individual	1
25	Green Perceived Organizational Support	Individual	2
26	Green Goal Difficulty	Individual	1
27	Pro-environmental psychological capital	Individual	1
28	Job Embeddedness	Individual	1
29	Employee green self-accountability	Individual	1
30	Reflected Moral Attractiveness	Individual	1
31	Green Absorption Capacity	Individual	1
32	Perceived behavioural Control	Individual	1
33	Connectedness to nature	Individual	1
34	Green Behaviour	Individual	7
35	Employees felt responsibility for the environment	Individual	1
36	Employee green attitude	individual	1
37	Emotional exhaustion	Individual	1
38	Pro-environmental behaviour	Individual	3
39	Green work climate perception	Individual	1

Moderating variables help in modifying the strength or weakness between an independent and a dependent variable. These variables may affect the relationship between antecedent and the outcomes in many ways like they can strengthen, weaken or negate the relationship between them. These variables offer a more thorough explanation in order to understand the influence of correlation between these two variables (MacKinnon 2011). As mentioned in Table-2, various moderators have been used between green HRM and employee green behaviour. Around 68% of these moderators are at the individual level like individual green values, environmental knowledge, employee green training and development and 32.14% of the moderators are at the organizational level. An insightful finding is that majority of the moderators (17.86%) have used leadership variables such as servant leadership, environmentally specific servant leadership, ethical leadership, responsible and spiritual leadership. In a dynamic environment, leadership can play a critical role in determining the effectiveness of plans and in establishing competitive edge. A crucial aspect of management is leadership, which contributes to the efficiency and efficacy of an organization's financial and nonfinancial performance (Bourini et al. 2015). Findings also reveal that there is no moderator which is at the team level because of rising uncertainties in the team dynamics and team complexities (Sparks et al., 2015).

Table 2: Moderating variables used at Individual, Team and Organizational level

Serial Number	Variables	Individual/ Team/ Organizational Level	No. of Studies
1	Servant Leadership	Organizational	1
2	Environmental Values	Organizational	2
3	Environmentally-specific servant leadership	Organizational	1
4	HRM system strength	Organizational	1
5	Green HRM	Organizational	2
6	Ethical Leadership	Organizational	1
7	Responsible Leadership	Organizational	1
8	Spiritual Leadership	Individual	1
9	Environmental Value Discrepancy	Individual	1
10	Gender	Individual	1
11	Individual Green Values	Individual	4
12	Environmental Knowledge	Individual	3
13	Intrinsic Spirituality	Individual	1
14	Employee green training and development	Individual	3
15	Employee green participation and involvement	Individual	2
16	Employee green performance management and appraisal	Individual	1
17	Employee green compensation and rewards	Individual	2

A framework depicting the relationship green HRM and employee green behaviour through the mediators and moderators at individual, team and organizational level has been presented in figure-2.

Figure - 2

3.3 Theoretical frameworks of Green HRM and Employee green behaviour

In this section an attempt is made to study various theories used in green HRM and employee green behaviour researchers. The application of theories in research has several advantages. Theories describe the main causes, consequences, processes and underlying mechanisms of the occurrence of natural or social phenomena (Pramling 2023).

Additionally, they facilitate the process of reconciling uneven data by identifying situational factors impacting the link between two dimensions and help in integrating previous empirical findings inside a theoretical framework (Bacharach 1989).

By assisting in the identification of constructs and interactions that require additional investigation, theories can offer direction for upcoming studies. Lastly, theories can also help in generating cumulative knowledge by reevaluating our understanding of existing assumptions (Whetten 1989).

Table-3 represents the theories used in the literature establishing the relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour. Multiple theories from various disciplines like psychology (36.36%), social psychology (13.64%), sociology (9.09%), ecology (9.09%), organizational behaviour (9.09%), HRM (4.55%), operations (4.55%), Industrial/Organizational (I/O) psychology (4.55%), economics (4.55%) and communication (4.55%) have been used indicating researchers' dependence on a multidisciplinary approach of research.

Table 3: Theories used

Serial Number	Theories	Discipline	No of studies	Percentage
1	Social identity Theory	Social Psychology	14	21.88
2	Ability-Motivation-Opportunity Theory	HRM	10	15.63
3	Social Exchange Theory	Sociology	10	15.63
4	Value Belief Norm Theory	Social Psychology	3	4.69
5	Theory of Planned Behaviour	Psychology	3	4.69
6	Social Cognitive Theory	Psychology	3	4.69
7	Supply -Value-Fit Theory	Operations	3	4.69
8	Social Learning Theory	Sociology	2	3.13
9	Conservation of Resources	Ecology	2	3.13
10	Goal-Setting Theory	Industrial/Organizational (I/O) psychology	2	3.13
11	Theory of Normative Conduct	Social Psychology	1	1.56
12	Theory of Anticipated Emotions	Psychology	1	1.56
13	Theory of Convergence-Emergence	Economics	1	1.56
14	Corporate Environmentalism Theory	Ecology	1	1.56
15	Organizational Support Theory	Psychology	1	1.56
16	Person-Environment Fit Theory	Psychology	1	1.56
17	Social Information Processing Theory	Communication	1	1.56
18	Attitude Theory	Psychology	1	1.56
19	Attribution Theory	Psychology	1	1.56
20	Self-Determination Theory	Human Behaviour	1	1.56
21	Job Embeddedness Theory	Organizational Behaviour	1	1.56
22	Reformulation of Attitude Theory	Psychology	1	1.56

The top eight theories that have been used more frequently by researchers are as follows:

- **Social identity Theory (SIT)**

This theory has been most widely used in the literature of green HRM and employee green behaviour. According to social identity theory, when a person puts their social circle into inner and outer groups, they will change their attitudes and behaviours to become more like other members of the inner group and more unlike members of the outer group (Tajfel and Turner 2004). SIT has been used in different contexts in these studies for example., few studies suggest that, employees feel pride in belonging to an organisation that upholds socially desirable principles and are quick to identify with it (Dutton et al. 1994; Tajfel and Turner 1979). This claim has been supported by the findings of the research carried out by Maxwell and Knox (2009), who found that an organization's external reputation encourages its workforce to identify with it. Genuine concern for environmental sustainability builds the organization's reputation externally and motivates staff to join it by demonstrating their own green commitment. Employees with a social identity who care about the environment always act in a green manner (Unsworth et al. 2021).

- **Ability-Motivation-Opportunity Theory (AMO)**

AMO theory proposed by Bailey (1993) is based on the assumption that employee's continuous effort requires three key components, which are skills, motivation and an opportunity to participate. It is believed that performance is a result of employees' ability (i.e., capacity to accomplish a particular task), motivation (i.e., demonstrated willingness by employees) and

opportunity (resulting from individuals' self-directed leadership) in attaining the shared objective of the organization (Nehles et al. 2023). Additionally, Vroom (1964) argued that motivation and aptitude are key factors in achieving performance. AMO is a commonly utilised theoretical framework in HRM (Nehles et al. 2013; Obeidat et al. 2016; Renwick et al. 2013). Organisations that practice green HRM (Amrutha and Geetha, 2020; Cabral & Dhar, 2019): (a) hire staff with green skills and abilities; (b) inspire staff through training and development; and (c) provide staff with opportunity to participate in green initiatives. Employees are motivated by the performance appraisal system (Fawehinmi et al. 2020). Negative appraisals will provide opportunity for green participation and enhance performance, while positive evaluations motivate them on to achieve outstanding green performance. Researches have shown that if employees want to exhibit green behaviour in their organizations, then, they need to perform certain competencies to perform voluntary green tasks. Therefore, green HRM activities should be implemented in the direction which enhance the abilities of the employees to acquire these competencies. Secondly, employees must be motivated in a way such that even if their job description may not specifically address it, employees nevertheless need to be driven to complete tasks and duties connected to the environment. Thirdly, opportunities must be provided to the employees to pursue green tasks (Veerasingam et al. 2023). AMO has been suggested by earlier researchers as a means of elucidating the connection between individual employee behaviour and green HRM procedures (Ababneh 2021; Renwick et al. 2013). According to the AMO theory, an organization's ability to perform sustainably depends on how well it gives its workers the chance to demonstrate environmentally friendly behaviour, encourages them to do so by rewarding them when they do so, and fosters an environment where workers can become more knowledgeable about and adept at implementing environmentally friendly practices (Anwar et al. 2020; Singh et al. 2020).

- **Social Exchange Theory (SET)**

The relationship between green HRM and employee green conduct is theoretically explained by the social exchange theory (Blau 1964). According to this theory, social exchange occurs when "a person is drawn to another person, if he expects himself being associated with that person, will be in some way rewarding for himself, and his interest in the expected social rewards draws him to the other" (Blau 1964).

Green HRM practices enhance employees' green behaviour by increasing their understanding of the environment (Aboramadan 2022). Organisational leaders who participate in and carry out green projects inspire their staff to do the same. Due to this social interaction, employees form a bond with their company (Cropanzano and Mitchell 2005). If both parties follow the exchange norms, there is a very high possibility that employees and their organisation trust one another. Employees demonstrate green conduct in return when organisations are required to work towards environmental sustainability through various green HRM initiatives like green goals, green recruitment, green training, and green performance management (Renwick et al. 2013).

The green initiatives in this case impose a duty on the staff to act sustainably. As a result, in exchange for the company's investment in green HRM programmes, employees engage in behaviours that protect and benefit the environment. This makes the claim that an organization's green HRM practices could encourage its employees' green behaviour and increase their propensity for environmental sustainability credible (Dumont et al. 2017).

- **Value-Belief-Norm Theory (VBN)**

According to Stern et al. (1999), people's work behaviour is influenced by their own values, beliefs, and norms. VBN theory, along with the norm-activation theory, personal values theory, and the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP), have used to synthesise the process of environmental behavioural activation (Dunlap and Van Liere 1978). The model highlights individual green values and ideas that contribute to environmental behaviour while explaining how people behave in an environmentally friendly way. To put it more precisely, a person's green beliefs and NEP perspectives have an impact on their environmental opinions and ecological concerns. Literature has shown a strong correlation between a person's ideals and their environmental friendliness. Andersson, Shivarajan, and Blau (2005) shared that people who value the environment are more likely to display eco-friendly behaviours, similarly, Chou (2014) has noted that people who appreciate the environment show eco-friendly behaviour at work. Cheema et al. (2020) have also asserted that green values are likely to influence individuals' in-role and extra-role behaviours, and that effective environmental management develops if individual and organisational green values are compatible.

- **Theory of planned behaviour (TPB)**

The TPB model by Karampour and Bojarpour's (2012) is used to predict the behaviour of the individual which are determined by three important factors: attitudes towards the behaviour, subjective norms and perceived behavioural control. This perception-attitude-behaviour approach creates a framework to understand unique behavioural patterns among individuals. This theory assumes that employees' perception of green HRM fosters a positive attitude towards the workplace, inspiring employees to act in a way that promotes environmental conservation and safety (De Leeuw et al. 2015). TPB assumes that a person's intention to carry out a behaviour is considered as the antecedent because it attributes attitudes to behaviour (Ajzen et al. 2011). According to Norton et al. (2014) employees' perceptions of organisational standards and commitments, as well as co-workers' environmentalist attitudes and actions, are some significant factors that affect pro-environmental behaviour. Also perceived behavioural control is thought to be determined by perception of individuals facilitating about green HRM, as these ideas regarding perceived green HRM imply the existence of elements that encourage employee adoption of pro-environmental behaviour (Zibarras and Coan 2015).

- **Social Cognitive Theory (SCT)**

According to social cognitive theory (Bandura 2001), a person's knowledge acquisition can sometimes be directly linked to what they observe in other people's social interactions, experiences, education, and how external factors affect them. External variables affect a person's ability to consciously select, carry out, and control their own actions to get desired results. From a socio-cognitive standpoint, individuals respond differently to outside influences and are quick and capable of self-adjustment (Bandura 2001). When workers experience a greater awareness of their environment and its significance, they are actively engaged in addressing the environmental issues. The primary goal of green HRM is to increase awareness in the employees regarding the complexities of managing the environment, and about the actions required to solve the issues (Ahmad 2015). According to social cognitive theory, green HRM affects the functioning of employees by increasing their awareness towards the environment (Darvishmotevali and Altinay 2022). An effective training program on enhancing environmental awareness help in building

employees' skills on how to protect their ecosystem (Daily et al. 2012; Fern'andez et al. 2003). According to Kim et al. (2019) human resource managers should therefore, offer their staff green systems and environmental protection training programs, which would assist staff members in comprehending environmental policies and realizing the significance of environmental protection, which would cause them to become pro-active towards environment.

- **Supply Value Fit Theory (SVF)**

The SVF theory posits that employee work attitudes and behaviour will improve, if personal values align with organisational values (Edwards 1996; Edwards and Shipp 2007). While it may seem obvious that there exist some conflicts between an individual's values and those of the organisation in which he or she works, it is in the organization's best interest to work towards congruent shared values (Paarlberg and Perry 2007). The best outcomes for employees are anticipated to come from a shared ideology that harmonises individual values with those of the organisation (Edwards 1996; Edwards and Cable 2009; Paarlberg and Perry 2007). Examples of these outcomes include strengthened organisational identification and meaning of work, as well as positive work attitudes and behaviour. The possibility that an employee commits to accomplishing organisational goals and objectives increases with how strongly the individual connects with his or her organisation through shared values and identification (Cohen and Liu 2011). Employee behaviour, therefore, as stated by Day and Bedeian (1991), is the result of the interaction between the individual and the environment. The central tenets of the supplies-values fit theory (Edwards 1996; Edwards and Shipp 2007) is that if an organisation provides an environment that is supportive of an employee's values and as a result the employee's green values are compatible with those of the organisation, it would be expected that the employee would be more likely to exhibit green workplace behaviours. In contrast, employees would be less likely to exhibit green behaviour at work if their values conflict with those of the organisation or if the organisation does not provide an environment that meets their needs. Therefore, employee workplace green behaviour is influenced by both personal and organisational environmental ideals.

- **Social Learning Theory (SLT)**

The SLT (Bandura 1969) is based on the assumption that people learn by observing others. Employees in the organizations observe, imitate and reinforce the behaviour of others. In the context of green HRM, employees develop pro-environmental attitudes by observing the green practices of employees or their respective supervisors (Darvishmotevali and Altinay, 2022). When an employee practices green behaviour in the organization, others get imitated from that behaviour and reinforce it in their day-to-day operations. In addition to assisting followers in realizing their own potential, servant leaders encourage their followers' service-oriented actions within the organization by giving them more authority and via the process of role-modelling, they provide their followers the chance to study and replicate the actions of the leader (Liden et al. 2014).

If we analyse the most frequently used theories used in the green HRM and employee literature, these theories are majorly from disciplines like psychology, sociology, social psychology, human behaviour etc. and from the social science domain. As the researches on green HRM and employee green behaviour are carried out in the organizational context and organizations are social entities, theories from psychology, sociology, social psychology, human behaviour pose to be more relevant. However, very limited theories from other disciplines like economics, communication, marketing,

finance etc. have been used. Theoretical extension, by using the theories of other disciplines may help in building a broader and better perspective to the literature of green HRM and employee green behaviour.

4. IMPLICATIONS

- **Theoretical implications**

This SLR offers the following theoretical implications. Firstly, there have been many studies conducted in the past on green HRM and employee green behaviour separately but no research attention has been given to comprehensively map the literature linking green HRM and employee green behaviour. As per our knowledge, this is the first systematic literature review that has taken into consideration both the variables together and offers a holistic perspective. Secondly, the review reveals that various mediators and moderators have been used in empirical and quantitative studies and segregates them at individual, team and organizational levels. Mapping these would in turn help explain how and under what boundary conditions, green HRM impacts employee green behaviour. Appreciation of intervening variables (mediators) aids in understanding what transmits the effect of green HRM on employee green behaviour and thus helps reduce parameter bias (Preacher and Hayes 2008). This will also help the researchers to overcome biases and prejudices. Additionally, acknowledgment of boundary conditions (moderators) helps understand which variables affect the nature of relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour (Howell et al. 1986; MacKinnon 2011). Thirdly, this review culls out various theories that explain relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour. It is observed that majority of the theories used in various studies have been adapted from twin disciplines of psychology and social psychology emphasising on different behavioural aspects of the relationship, which is the focus of these studies.

- **Practical Implications**

The findings of this research are likely to provide valuable insights on an important aspect of HRM (green behaviour and green business), hitherto ignored and neglected, to the managers and the practitioners. This study will help leaders and the managers design strategies aimed at adopting effective green HRM practices and policies in organisations that will be responsible for shaping green behaviour of the employees. This SLR offers the following practical lessons. Firstly, this SLR guides the practitioners' regarding the various seminal green HRM practices responsible for shaping green behaviour of employees at workplace. Second, this SLR also points out which conditions must be facilitated at the individual, team and organizational level that strengthens the influence of green HRM on employee green behaviour. For instance, individual green values have emerged as the most frequently used moderator suggesting that individuals with green values tend to exhibit more green behaviours in the organization when exposed to green HRM practices. This insight can be used in shaping the recruitment and selection practice so as to encourage more employee participation in environmental performance of the organization. Research has also noted that individuals with high green values better aligns with the organization's mission and vision (Wang et al. 2018). Additionally, when providing training to the employees who score high on individual green values, the chances for their green work engagement and green commitment stands high (Mi et al. 2021). Thirdly, the understanding of the mediators at various levels would

help practitioners in fathoming the psychological process through which green HRM has an effect on employee green behaviour.

Lastly, it is advisable for organisations to incorporate green HRM practices and responsibilities across all levels inside the organisation. This can be done by integrating green HRM goals and practices into the information management system, where the mediators and moderators relevant to the development and delivery of green HRM and green behaviours are mapped into the workforce planning and performance evaluation systems, respectively. This is also significant to exhibit the right set of green behaviour across all levels. When employee observes his supervisor or senior leadership is depicting these green behaviours, they will also be inspired to adapt these practices. This will help in framing an organizational culture which focuses on caring the environment and hence make sure that employees working in the organization should be more environment friendly and demonstrate green behaviour through better implementation of green HRM practices and policies.

5. POLICY RECOMMENDATION

Green HRM seems to have been taken very seriously today by all stakeholders involved in HRM, including practitioners, academics, employers, and employees. However, despite the flourishing literature on the topic, there remains a gap regarding its implementation in organizations (Ahmad 2015). It is suggested therefore that there is a need to bridge the gap between formulation of green HRM practices and their implementation in order to ensure employee green behaviour in organizations. It is also observed that "Green HRM" has a significant scope in the field of management research but there is scant interest in the theme in the academic field. Nevertheless, it is anticipated that there will be more studies on this subject in the near future in academics, given the growing sensitivity towards environment worldwide, and this is likely to lead to HRM practices which may engender green projects and have an impact on environmental management plans. In this regard, studies that look at the overall effects of GHRM systems as opposed to specific practices would be very beneficial. In the context of Asia, policy makers should frame such policies which are focused on social and environmental rules and regulations in order to focus on the long-term sustainability at the workplace.

Lessons learnt from the studies outlined in this SLR can assist organizations in addressing the issue environmental degradation, improving their financial and physical health, and creating a cleaner, safer environment (Tipu 2022). It can also be emphasized here that HR plays a critical role in bringing about such green transformation by developing green HRM practices and policies and shaping employee actions and behaviour proactively (Shahzad et al. 2023). The HR can set the ball rolling by emphasizing on hiring new workers who are more conscious of environment-friendly corporate practices. It can also make a big difference in the company's green movement by encouraging, supporting, and pushing the staff persistently to adopt green practices for more environmentally friendly business operations.

6. LIMITATIONS OF STUDY

This review has a few limitations. First, the SLR has limited its scope only to the ABDC database. Future researchers should expand it by taking ABS and FT-50 journal lists into consideration to get a broader understanding of the theme. Systematic literature reviews in future should incorporate

empirical qualitative research and mixed method studies as these could provide better insights into how actually green HRM practices and employee green behaviours ensure green and effective organisational performance. Secondly, the information on the databases changes frequently in so far as the number of research articles are concerned (Valenzuela-Fernandez et al. 2019). Thirdly, the present SLR has not taken into consideration papers from proceedings, retracted publications, books, book chapters, conference papers, meeting abstracts, and review articles which could have offered a holistic perspective to future researchers. Fourthly, the choice of keywords is based on the existing literature and hence, there is every chance of the SLR having missed out on related keywords.

7. SCOPE FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The findings indicate that the studies covered in the SLR focus mostly on traditional green HRM practices like green recruitment and selection, green training and development, green performance management and green compensation and rewards. Future researches can take up related areas like green induction, green safety, green institutional initiatives, green discipline management etc for empirical study in order to bring about a holistic overview of the concept. Similarly, future researchers can bring scholarly attention to recently emerged sub-dimensions of employee green behaviour such as employee's eco-friendly behaviour and green voice behaviour.

This review is primarily based on research works on green HRM and green behaviour of employees. There is a common theme running through these studies that in order to promote green behaviour, organisations should focus on environment-related organisational changes as well as employee attitudes and interpretations of green HRM practices followed. For instance, businesses could sponsor surveys aimed at mapping out employee satisfaction to see how their staff members feel about the compatibility of green HRM and their employee perception on execution of those practices. Organisations could also promote information sharing to learn how staff members interpret environmental messages shared through green HRM practices and measure them to improve the green behaviour of employees.

Secondly, it is suggested that green HRM systems should support employee-driven initiatives given the fact most organisations face the challenge of resource constraints while adapting themselves to the demands for green production. Three categories of discretionary employee behaviours related to environment were found by Boiral and Paillé (2012), i.e., eco-initiatives, eco-helping, and eco-civic. They imply that such organisational citizenship behaviours can be directed outside the workplace in the form of individual initiatives— toward coworkers in the form of reciprocal assistance and towards the organisation in the form of support for the organization's commitments. It is very much recommended that resource constraints should be handled very carefully making a right balance between implementation of green HRM practices and green behaviours. Overutilization of these resources can disturb the efficiency of the organizations and underutilization can prohibit employees in adopting these behaviours. So, it is imperative for organizations to maintain a right balance of the both.

Thirdly, it is advisable for organisations to incorporate green HRM practices and responsibilities across all levels inside the organisation, considering the importance of green HRM in the organisation. This can be done, for instance, by integrating green HRM goals and practices into the information management system, where the mediators and moderators relevant to the

development and delivery of green HRM and green behaviours are mapped into the workforce planning and performance evaluation systems, respectively. It is also significant to exhibit the right set of green behaviour across all levels. When an executive employee observes his supervisor or seniors incorporating these green behaviours in their task-related activities, they will also be inspired to adopt these practices irrespective of levels lower, middle and upper.

Findings also highlight the role of mediators and moderators at individual, team and organizational levels. However, very few studies have studied mediators and moderators at the team level. As organization is a combination of different groups and teams, at this level, sociology, social psychology, and anthropology are crucial disciplines which can shed light on the theme being explored here. Even organizational behaviour can be another important area which examines group dynamics, organisational conflicts, politics, communication, etc. Managers can generate ideas on how to manage and lead groups in the organisation by examining the behaviour of group-level actors. Future researchers can include group dynamics, group decisions, group politics, team communication, group norms, group roles and group cohesiveness which can aid managers in better understanding on how groups operate and how to increase their effectiveness and efficiency. Managers can improve the performance and satisfaction of groups or teams inside the organisation by designing appropriate interventions, such as team building, training, reward systems, or conflict resolution procedures, by analysing team level characteristics.

In the present SLR, different theories have been used by the researchers which have been adapted from disciplines like psychology, social psychology and organizational behaviour. However, future researchers can integrate theories from other related domains like marketing, operations, communication and information technology. Such expanded inter-disciplinary engagements will add to quality and content of research and enhance HR understanding on the subject. Testing the validity and robustness of various theories grounded in diverse contexts or domains could add to the predictive and operative aspects of research and aid practitioners constantly looking for better and more effective green HR practices. Sociological theories can be used to explain the intricacy and vagueness present in green HRM and green behaviour events. Institutional theory can encourage studies that further comprehend how green HRM systems and green behaviour spread across sectors and nations (Hoffman 1999; Peng 2002). Investigating the impact of formal institutional change and shifting social norms of green HRM, and green behaviour can address the question of whether organisations should use a consistent approach across contexts or use a customised approach to consider local contexts. Another interesting approach to identifying paradoxes relating to the application of green HRM and green behaviour systems is the paradox-of-society concept. For instance, focusing more on adopting green behaviours using green HRM practices in order to enhance environmental goals may make financial shortages more likely and have a negative impact on economic and social performance Guerci and Carollo (2016) of an organisation.

8. CONCLUSION

This systematic literature review has synthesized scholarly investigations into the relationship between green HRM practices and employee green behaviour. The first research question deals with conceptualization of green HRM and employee green behaviour and its sub-dimensions in order to understand both these variables and their origin and evolution. The second research question dwells on different research samples used in the literature. The third research question

focuses on various methods and the tools used to perform analysis in the empirical quantitative researches on green HRM and employee green behaviour. The fourth and fifth research questions deal with frameworks which identify several mediators and moderators of green HRM and employee green behaviour at individual, team and organizational levels. The sixth and the last research question seeks to identify the theoretical frameworks establishing relationship between green HRM and employee green behaviour. As green HRM and its effect on employee green behaviour is still a relatively new area, diverse theoretical views have not yet been harnessed well to determine which one or group of theories would be most helpful for adaptation by organisations for ensuring their green compliance. There is a new academic discipline emerging in the horizon thanks to the continued focus on environmental sustainability, the emerging green HRM practices and study of their relationship with and impact on employee green behaviour. It is hoped that future research on these themes would provide fresh perspectives on how management, employment, and organisations are transforming themselves not just in Asia but globally to demonstrate their green behaviour and responsibilities towards environment.

References

- 1) Ababneh, O. M. A. (2021). How do green HRM practices affect employees' green behaviors? The role of employee engagement and personality attributes. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 64(7), 1204-1226.
- 2) Aboramadan, M. (2022). The effect of green HRM on employee green behaviors in higher education: the mediating mechanism of green work engagement. *International Journal of Organizational Analysis*, 30(1), 7-23.
- 3) Aboramadan, M., & Karatepe, O. M. (2021). Green human resource management, perceived green organizational support and their effects on hotel employees' behavioral outcomes. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 33(10), 3199-3222.
- 4) Ahmad, S. (2015). Green human resource management: Policies and practices. *Cogent business & management*, 2(1), 1030817.
- 5) Ajzen, I., Joyce, N., Sheikh, S., & Cote, N. G. (2011). Knowledge and the prediction of behavior: The role of information accuracy in the theory of planned behavior. *Basic and applied social psychology*, 33(2), 101-117.
- 6) Amrutha, V. N., & Geetha, S. N. (2020). A systematic review on green human resource management: Implications for social sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner production*, 247, 119131.
- 7) Andersson, L., Shivarajan, S., & Blau, G. (2005). Enacting ecological sustainability in the MNC: A test of an adapted value-belief-norm framework. *Journal of business ethics*, 59, 295-305.
- 8) Anwar, N., Mahmood, N. H. N., Yusliza, M. Y., Ramayah, T., Faezah, J. N., & Khalid, W. (2020). Green Human Resource Management for organisational citizenship behaviour towards the environment and environmental performance on a university campus. *Journal of cleaner production*, 256, 120401.

- 9) Arulrajah, A. A., Opatha, H. H. D. N. P., & Nawaratne, N. N. J. (2015). Green human resource management practices: A review.
- 10) Bacharach, S. B. (1989). Organizational theories: Some criteria for evaluation. *Academy of management review*, 14(4), 496-515.
- 11) Bailey, T. R. (1993). Discretionary effort and the organization of work: Employee participation and work reform since Hawthorne. Teachers College and Conservation of Human Resources, Columbia University.
- 12) Bandura, A. (1969). Social-learning theory of identificatory processes. *Handbook of socialization theory and research*, 213, 262.
- 13) Bandura, A. (2001). Social cognitive theory: An agentic perspective. *Annual review of psychology*, 52(1), 1-26.
- 14) Blau, P. M. (1964). Justice in social exchange. *Sociological inquiry*, 34(2), 193-206.
- 15) Boiral, O., & Paillé, P. (2012). Organizational citizenship behaviour for the environment: Measurement and validation. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 109(4): 431-445.
- 16) Bos-Nehles, A. C., Van Riemsdijk, M. J., & Kees Looise, J. (2013). Employee perceptions of line management performance: applying the AMO theory to explain the effectiveness of line managers' HRM implementation. *Human resource management*, 52(6), 861-877.
- 17) Bos-Nehles, A., Townsend, K., Cafferkey, K., & Trullen, J. (2023). Examining the Ability, Motivation and Opportunity (AMO) framework in HRM research: Conceptualization, measurement and interactions. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 25(4), 725-739.
- 18) Bourini, F., Abu-Rumman, H. A., & Alhadid, Y. A. (2015). The impact of leadership style as a moderator variable on the relationship between leadership practices and organizational performance analytical study on Jordanian commercial banks. *Journal of Advanced Social Research*, 5(2), 1-10.
- 19) Cabral, C., & Dhar, R. L. (2019). Skill development research in India: a systematic literature review and future research agenda. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 26(7), 2242-2266.
- 20) Chaudhary, R. (2020). Green human resource management and employee green behavior: an empirical analysis. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(2), 630-641.
- 21) Cheema, S., Afsar, B., & Javed, F. (2020). Employees' corporate social responsibility perceptions and organizational citizenship behaviors for the environment: The mediating roles of organizational identification and environmental orientation fit. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 27(1), 9-21.
- 22) Chou, C.-J. (2014). Hotels' environmental policies and employee personal environmental beliefs: Interactions and outcomes. *Tourism Management*, 40, 436-446.

- 23) Ciocirlan, C. E. (2017). Environmental workplace behaviors: Definition matters. *Organization & Environment*, 30(1), 51-70.
- 24) Cropanzano, R., & Mitchell, M. S. (2005). Social exchange theory: An interdisciplinary review. *Journal of management*, 31(6), 874-900.
- 25) Dada, O. (2018). A model of entrepreneurial autonomy in franchised outlets: A systematic review of the empirical evidence. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 20(2), 206–226.
- 26) Daily, B. F., Bishop, J. W., & Massoud, J. A. (2012). The role of training and empowerment in environmental performance: A study of the Mexican maquiladora industry. *International Journal of operations & production management*, 32(5), 631-647.
- 27) Darvishmotevali, M., & Altinay, L. (2022). Green HRM, environmental awareness and green behaviors: The moderating role of servant leadership. *Tourism Management*, 88, 104401.
- 28) De Leeuw, A., Valois, P., Ajzen, I., & Schmidt, P. (2015). Using the theory of planned behavior to identify key beliefs underlying pro-environmental behavior in high-school students: Implications for educational interventions. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 42, 128-138.
- 29) Di Vaio, A., Hassan, R., Chhabra, M., Arrigo, E., & Palladino, R. (2022). Sustainable entrepreneurship impact and entrepreneurial venture life cycle: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 378, 134469.
- 30) Dumont, J., Shen, J., & Deng, X. (2017). Effects of green HRM practices on employee workplace green behavior: The role of psychological green climate and employee green values. *Human resource management*, 56(4), 613-627.
- 31) Dunlap, R. E., & Van Liere, K. D. (1978). The “new environmental paradigm”. *The journal of environmental education*, 9(4), 10-19.
- 32) Dutton, J. E., Dukerich, J. M., & Harquail, C. V. (1994). Organizational images and member identification. *Administrative science quarterly*, 239-263.
- 33) Edwards, I. R., & Shipp, A. I. (2007). The relationship between person-environment fit and outcomes: An integrative. *Perspectives on organizational fit*, 209, 109-142.
- 34) Edwards, J. R. (1996). An examination of competing versions of the person-environment fit approach to stress. *Academy of Management Journal*, 39(2), 292–339.
- 35) Edwards, J. R., & Cable, D. M. (2009). The value of value congruence. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 94(3), 654–677.
- 36) Fawehinmi, O., Yusliza, M. Y., Mohamad, Z., Noor Faezah, J., & Muhammad, Z. (2020). Assessing the green behaviour of academics: The role of green human resource management and environmental knowledge. *International Journal of Manpower*, 41(7), 879-900.
- 37) Fernández, E., Junquera, B., & Ordiz, M. (2003). Organizational culture and human resources in the environmental issue: a review of the literature. *International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 14(4), 634-656.

- 38) Foster, M. K. (2014). Data collection for team research: assessing the impact of virtuality on team effectiveness. SAGE Publications, Ltd.
- 39) Guerci, M., & Carollo, L. (2016). A paradox view on green human resource management: Insights from the Italian context. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 27(2), 212-238.
- 40) Hoffman, A. J. (1999). Institutional evolution and change: Environmentalism and the US chemical industry. *Academy of Management Journal*, 42(4): 351–371.
- 41) Hooi, L. W., Liu, M. S., & Lin, J. J. (2022). Green human resource management and green organizational citizenship behavior: do green culture and green values matter?. *International Journal of Manpower*, 43(3), 763-785.
- 42) Howell, J. P., Dorfman, P. W., & Kerr, S. (1986). Moderator variables in leadership research. *Academy of management review*, 11(1), 88-102.
- 43) Jackson, S. E. (2012). Building empirical foundations to inform the future practice of environmental sustainability. *Managing human resources for environmental sustainability*, 416-432.
- 44) Jackson, S. E., & Seo, J. (2010). The greening of strategic HRM scholarship. *Organization Management Journal*, 7(4), 278-290.
- 45) Kamboj, S., & Rahman, Z. (2015). Marketing capabilities and firm performance: literature review and future research agenda. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 64(8), 1041-1067.
- 46) Karampour, S., & Bojarpour, M. (2012). An implementation of TPB method for learning important factors influencing knowledge sharing. *Management Science Letters*, 2(7), 2293-2300.
- 47) Katz, I. M., Rauvola, R. S., Rudolph, C. W., & Zacher, H. (2022). Employee green behavior: A meta-analysis. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 29(5), 1146-1157.
- 48) Kauppi, K., Salmi, A., & You, W. (2018). Sourcing from Africa: A systematic review and a research agenda. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 20(2), 627–650.
- 49) Kim, Y. J., Kim, W. G., Choi, H. M., & Phetvaroon, K. (2019). The effect of green human resource management on hotel employees' eco-friendly behavior and environmental performance. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 76, 83–93.
- 50) Kramar, R. (2014). Beyond strategic human resource management: is sustainable human resource management the next approach?. *The international journal of human resource management*, 25(8), 1069-1089.
- 51) Kramer, M. R., & Porter, M. (2011). *Creating shared value* (Vol. 17). Boston, MA, USA: FSG.
- 52) Leonidou, L. C., Christodoulides, P., Kyrgidou, L. P., & Palihawadana, D. (2017). Internal drivers and performance consequences of small firm green business strategy: The moderating role of external forces. *Journal of business ethics*, 140, 585-606.

- 53) Liden, R. C., Wayne, S. J., Liao, C., & Meuser, J. D. (2014). Servant leadership and serving culture: Influence on individual and unit performance. *Academy of management journal*, 57(5), 1434-1452.
- 54) MacKinnon, D. P. (2011). Integrating mediators and moderators in research design. *Research on social work practice*, 21(6), 675-681.
- 55) MacKinnon, D. P., Coxe, S., & Baraldi, A. N. (2012). Guidelines for the investigation of mediating variables in business research. *Journal of business and psychology*, 27, 1-14.
- 56) Masri, H. A., & Jaaron, A. A. (2017). Assessing green human resources management practices in Palestinian manufacturing context: An empirical study. *Journal of cleaner production*, 143, 474-489.
- 57) Maxwell, R., & Knox, S. (2009). Motivating employees to "live the brand": a comparative case study of employer brand attractiveness within the firm. *Journal of marketing management*, 25(9-10), 893-907.
- 58) Mi, L., Sun, Y., Gan, X., Yang, Y., Jia, T., Wang, B., & Xu, T. (2021). Predicting environmental citizenship behavior in the workplace: A new perspective of environmental affective event. *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 27, 2037-2046.
- 59) Moola, S., Munn, Z., Sears, K., Sfecu, R., Currie, M., Lisy, K., Tufanaru, C., Qureshi, R., Mattis, P., & Mu, P. (2015). Conducting systematic reviews of association (etiology): The Joanna Briggs Institute's approach. *International Journal of Evidence-Based Healthcare*, 13(3), 163-169.
- 60) Nejati, M., Rabiei, S., & Jabbour, C. J. C. (2017). Envisioning the invisible: Understanding the synergy between green human resource management and green supply chain management in manufacturing firms in Iran in light of the moderating effect of employees' resistance to change. *Journal of cleaner production*, 168, 163-172.
- 61) Nisar, Q. A., Haider, S., Ali, F., Jamshed, S., Ryu, K., & Gill, S. S. (2021). Green human resource management practices and environmental performance in Malaysian green hotels: The role of green intellectual capital and pro-environmental behavior. *Journal of cleaner production*, 311, 127504.
- 62) Norton, T. A., Parker, S. L., Zacher, H., & Ashkanasy, N. M. (2015). Employee green behavior: A theoretical framework, multilevel review, and future research agenda. *Organization & Environment*, 28(1), 103-125.
- 63) Norton, T. A., Zacher, H., & Ashkanasy, N. M. (2014). Organisational sustainability policies and employee green behaviour: The mediating role of work climate perceptions. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 38, 49-54.
- 64) Obeidat, B. Y., Al-Suradi, M. M., Masa'deh, R. E., & Tarhini, A. (2016). The impact of knowledge management on innovation: An empirical study on Jordanian consultancy firms. *Management Research Review*, 39(10), 1214-1238.
- 65) Ones, D. S., & Dilchert, S. (2012). Environmental sustainability at work: A call to action. *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*, 5(4), 444-466.

- 66) Paarlberg, L. E., & Perry, J. L. (2007). Values management—aligning employee values and organizational goals. *American Review of Public Administration*, 37(4), 387–408.
- 67) Paillé, P., Boiral, O., & Chen, Y. (2013). Linking environmental management practices and organizational citizenship behaviour for the environment: a social exchange perspective. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 24(18), 3552-3575.
- 68) Paillé, P., Chen, Y., Boiral, O., & Jin, J. (2014). The impact of human resource management on environmental performance: An employee-level study. *Journal of Business ethics*, 121, 451-466.
- 69) Paillé, P., Valéau, P., & Renwick, D. W. (2020). Leveraging green human resource practices to achieve environmental sustainability. *Journal of cleaner production*, 260, 121137.
- 70) Paulet, R., Holland, P., & Morgan, D. (2021). A meta-review of 10 years of green human resource management: is Green HRM headed towards a roadblock or a revitalisation?. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 59(2), 159-183.
- 71) Peng, M. W. 2002. Towards an institution-based view of business strategy. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 19(2): 251–267.
- 72) Pham, D. D. T., & Paillé, P. (2020). Green recruitment and selection: an insight into green patterns. *International journal of manpower*, 41(3), 258-272.
- 73) Pramling, N. (2023). The Importance and Functions of Theory. In: *Methodology for Early Childhood Education and Care Research*. SpringerBriefs in Education. Springer, Cham
- 74) Preacher, K. J., & Hayes, A. F. (2008). Asymptotic and resampling strategies for assessing and comparing indirect effects in multiple mediator models. *Behavior research methods*, 40(3), 879-891.
- 75) Rayner, J., & Morgan, D. (2018). An empirical study of ‘green’workplace behaviours: ability, motivation and opportunity. *Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources*, 56(1), 56-78.
- 76) Ren, S., Tang, G., & E Jackson, S. (2018). Green human resource management research in emergence: A review and future directions. *Asia Pacific Journal of Management*, 35, 769-803.
- 77) Renwick, D. W., Redman, T., & Maguire, S. (2013). Green human resource management: A review and research agenda. *International journal of management reviews*, 15(1), 1-14.
- 78) Schaltegger, S., & Wagner, M. (2011). Sustainable entrepreneurship and sustainability innovation: categories and interactions. *Business strategy and the environment*, 20(4), 222-237.
- 79) Schaltegger, S., Beckmann, M., & Hansen, E. G. (2013). Transdisciplinarity in corporate sustainability: Mapping the field. *Business strategy and the environment*, 22(4), 219-229.
- 80) Shah, N., & Soomro, B. A. (2023). Effects of green human resource management practices on green innovation and behavior. *Management Decision*, 61(1), 290-312.
- 81) Shahzad, M. A., Jianguo, D., & Junaid, M. (2023). Impact of green HRM practices on sustainable performance: mediating role of green innovation, green culture, and green employees' behavior. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 30(38), 88524-88547.

- 82) Singh, S. K., Del Giudice, M., Chierici, R., & Graziano, D. (2020). Green innovation and environmental performance: The role of green transformational leadership and green human resource management. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 150, 119762.
- 83) Sparks, G. A., Herman, R., Wolfe, P., & Zurick, A. (2015). Leading through the complexities of team dynamics to achieve and sustain organizational goals. *Journal of Behavioral Studies in Business*, 8, 1.
- 84) Stern, P. C., Dietz, T., Abel, T., Guagnano, G. A., & Kalof, L. (1999). A value-belief-norm theory of support for social movements: The case of environmentalism. *Human ecology review*, 81-97.
- 85) Tajfel, H., & Turner, J. C. (2003). The social identity theory of intergroup behavior. *Social psychology*, 4, 73-98.
- 86) Tajfel, H., Turner, J. C., Austin, W. G., & Worchel, S. (1979). An integrative theory of intergroup conflict. *Organizational identity: A reader*, 56(65), 9780203505984-16.
- 87) Tang, G., Chen, Y., Jiang, Y., Paillé, P., & Jia, J. (2018). Green human resource management practices: scale development and validity. *Asia pacific journal of human resources*, 56(1), 31-55.
- 88) Tang, G., Ren, S., Wang, M., Li, Y., & Zhang, S. (2023). Employee green behaviour: A review and recommendations for future research. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, 25(2), 297-317.
- 89) Tanova, C., & Bayighomog, S. W. (2022). Green human resource management in service industries: the construct, antecedents, consequences, and outlook. *The Service Industries Journal*, 42(5-6), 412-452.
- 90) Taylor, S., Osland, J., & Egri, C. P. (2012). Guest editors' introduction: Introduction to HRM's role in sustainability: Systems, strategies, and practices. *Human Resource Management*, 51(6), 789-798.
- 91) Tipu, S. A. A. (2022). Organizational change for environmental, social, and financial sustainability: A systematic literature review. *Review of Managerial Science*, 16(6), 1697-1742.
- 92) Tranfield, D., Denyer, D., & Smart, P. (2003). Towards a methodology for developing evidence-informed management knowledge by means of systematic review. *British journal of management*, 14(3), 207-222.
- 93) Unsworth, K. L., Davis, M. C., Russell, S. V., & Bretter, C. (2021). Employee green behaviour: How organizations can help the environment. *Current Opinion in Psychology*, 42, 1-6.
- 94) Valenzuela-Fernandez, L., Merigó, J. M., Lichtenthal, J. D., & Nicolas, C. (2019). A bibliometric analysis of the first 25 years of the *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing*. *Journal of Business-to-Business Marketing*, 26(1), 75-94.
- 95) Van Dyne, L., Graham, J. W., & Dienesch, R. M. (1994). Organizational citizenship behavior: Construct redefinition, measurement, and validation. *Academy of management Journal*, 37(4), 765-802.

- 96) Veerasamy, U., Joseph, M. S., & Parayitam, S. (2023). Green human resource management practices and employee green behavior. *Journal of Environmental Planning and Management*, 1-27.
- 97) Vroom, V. H. (1964). *Work and motivation*.
- 98) Wagner M (2013) 'Green' human resource benefits: do they matter as determinants of environmental management system implementation? *Journal of Business Ethics* 114, 443-456.
- 99) Wang, C. L., & Chugh, H. (2014). Entrepreneurial learning: Past research and future challenges. *International journal of management reviews*, 16(1), 24-61.
- 100) Wang, X., Zhou, K., & Liu, W. (2018). Value congruence: a study of green transformational leadership and employee green behavior. *Frontiers in psychology*, 9, 1946.
- 101) Whetten, D. (1989). What constitutes a theoretical contribution? *Academy of Management Review*, 14(4), 490-495.
- 102) Ye, J., Yao, Y., & Li, L. (2022). The more involved, the more willing to participate: An analysis of the internal mechanism of positive spillover effects of pro-environmental behaviors. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 375, 133959.
- 103) Yong, J. Y., Yusliza, M. Y., & Fawehinmi, O. O. (2020). Green human resource management: A systematic literature review from 2007 to 2019. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 27(7), 2005-2027.
- 104) Yusoff, Y. M., Nejati, M., Kee, D. M. H., & Amran, A. (2020). Linking green human resource management practices to environmental performance in hotel industry. *Global Business Review*, 21(3), 663-680.
- 105) Zhang, Y., Luo, Y., Zhang, X., & Zhao, J. (2019). How green human resource management can promote green employee behavior in China: A technology acceptance model perspective. *Sustainability*, 11(19), 5408.
- 106) Zhao, X., & Huang, L. (2022). Understanding the dynamic role of natural resources, green technology, economic integration and social globalization towards sustainable environment in China. *Resources Policy*, 79, 103079.
- 107) Zibarras, L. D., & Coan, P. (2015). HRM practices used to promote pro-environmental behavior: a UK survey. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 26(16), 2121-2142.